

Fate of pesticides in the environment

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Abstract : The inherent bioactivity of agrochemicals demands their conscientious and careful use. As they may pollute the water, soil and air producing undesirable effects on human health, animal health and environment. Such effects may range from growth retardation to physiological or behavioral deficits which substantially affect the most sensitive individual or species, causing ecological changes.

The fate of pesticides introduced into the environment in any way e.g. through an application, a disposal or a spill is influenced by three major processes : adsorption, transfer and degradation.

Pesticide adsorption : Pesticide-adsorption in soil often occurs due to the binding of positively charged pesticide molecules and negatively charged clay particles. Strong attraction of pesticides by soil causes pest control reduction and plant injury by releasing adsorbed pesticide to sensitive rotational crop.

Pesticide transfer : Too much movement of pesticide can lead to reduced pest control, contamination of surface water and ground water and injury of non target species including humans. The transfer of pesticides may occur through : (1) Volatilization, (2) Runoff, (3) Leaching, (4) Absorption or uptake, (5) Crop removal.

Pesticide degradation : There are three types of pesticide degradation viz. (a) Microbial degradation, (b) Chemical degradation, (c) Photodegradation. Pesticides degradation or the breakdown of pesticides is usually considered beneficial.

Keywords : Pesticide, degradation, environment, sorption, photodegradation, chemical degradation, microbial degradation.

Introduction

The ever growing human population, which is expected to be 9.1 billion by 2050 (U.N., 2005) will require more agricultural production, especially in tropical regions. Increasing agricultural production in these regions relies on the use of agrochemicals, as shown by the growth of agrochemical market by approximately 4.5% annually. On one hand agricultural activity that now become essential in meeting with the dietary needs of the world population but on the other contamination of soil, air and water resources is increasing. Therefore, it becomes imperative to identify and quantify the chemical and biological processes that controlling the behavior of organic chemicals in the environment, to improve pesticidal management for minimize contamination of our natural resources and remediating contaminated environments. We know that pesticide means any substance intended for preventing, destroying, repelling or mitigating any insects, rodents, nematode, fungus, weed or any other form of terrestrial or aquatic plant, animal life or virus, bacte-

ria or other microorganism.

Worldwide we have an annual production of approximately 10^6 tons of active ingredients. Assuming a total arable land area of 13.8×10^6 km² on earth, enough, unrealistic, the even distribution of pesticides would amount to about $0.7 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$ (In India the consumption of pesticide is still low $0.5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1} \text{ yr}^{-1}$). This much use of organic chemicals by all the sectors of the economy is affecting human health and environment as a result of soil, air and water contamination. These effects may range from growth retardation to physiological or behavioral deficits which substantially affect the most sensitive individual or species^{1,2}. Subsequently, it may lead to population shift resulting in ecological changes. Because chemical technology is generally recognized as having great societal benefit compared to the risks, it is critical that the approaches and the tools for managing use of chemicals are developed in order to minimize future contamination. Hence, the new agrochemicals discovered and designed as pesticides are cost effective, having high bio-

logical efficacy and less persistence. We know that the efficacy of pesticide depends on various physico-chemical properties like water solubility, vapor pressure, polarity, particle size etc. Many of the newly developed pesticides, of which are applied at even rates one-tenth or less of conventional pesticides, are often found highly toxic to non target crops or aquatic organisms. Therefore, we must have definite information regarding the fate of these new chemicals. Of concern are also contaminant metabolites and transformation products which are in some instances more toxic and persistent than the parent molecule³.

When introduced into the environment fate of pesticide is influenced by three major processes : adsorption, transfer and degradation.

Fig. 1. The three major fate processes of pesticides in the environment are adsorption, transfer and degradation.

Pesticide adsorption : Sorption by organic matter (humus) and clay minerals are key processes affecting the fate and mobility of pesticides in soils. Adsorption means the transfer of a chemical species from one bulk phase of the surface to another phase. There it accumulates on the surface without penetrating the structure of the second phase. The finer soil particles (clays) possess greater total surface area, soils, consisting mainly of silt and clays; tend to adsorb higher concentration of pesticides than coarser soils. The major factors affecting adsorption on soil surface are : high molecular weight of pesticide; soil-

moisture content⁴; organic matter content^{5,6}; cation exchange capacity of soils⁷; particle size⁶; distribution⁷; pH⁸⁻¹⁰, dissolved organic matter^{9,11}, temperature¹², time factor^{13,14}; soil composition^{15,16}; physical and chemical characteristics of pesticidal compounds¹⁷ i.e. chemical character, configuration, water solubility charge distribution, polarity, microbial population¹⁸. Soil scientists^{19,20} have reported a positive correlation in between organic matter content, CEC of soil, DOM, time factor and adsorption, and a negative correlation in between soil, pH, soil-moisture content, temperature and adsorption.

Effect of time : Sorption and desorption processes differ in extent with timer. In general long contact time will allow molecular diffusion of pesticides to the smallest pores of soil particles which might result in strong sequestration and to the formation of strong bound pesticides residues^{13,14}.

Effect of pH : The pH is the most important parameter in the soil and several studies^{8,9} have been highlighted the significance of pH for adsorption and fate of pesticides. For anionic pesticides with increasing pH binding decreases¹⁰, so that desorption, mobility and transport increases. Wauchope *et al.*⁸ reviewed that soil pH changes have minor effect on the adsorption of non-ionic molecules where as sorption of pesticides with ionic equilibrium constants near the range of soil pH will be quite sensitive to the pH changes. The lowest sorption is expected when increasing soil pH weakly acidic pesticides ionizes so that they became anions. Then, repulsion from the mainly negatively charged soil surfaces increases and sorption decreases.

Effect of soil composition : The adsorption/fate of pesticides in soil are strongly influenced by the nature and properties of the present solute species. The presence of high concentration of anion decreases the adsorption of anionic pesticides due to competition for the same positive charged sorption sites¹⁵. While presence of multivalent cations such as Ca^{2+} enhanced the sorption of anionic pesticides¹⁵, due to formation of cationic bridges in between negatively charged group of soil and anionic pesticides¹⁶. Wauchope *et al.*⁸ reviewed that sorption of pesticides in dry soil or soils with non polar solvent increased. In general, it may be concluded that soil solution composition dictate the potential for retention and ultimate transport of pesticides to groundwater.

Effect of DOM : Addition of DOM strongly affects sorption, degradation and transport of pesticides⁹ because

it can form complexes with organic molecules and/or can compete with organic molecules for sorption sites. In contrast, the presence of DOM enhanced sorption due to co-adsorption of DOM-pesticide complexes onto the soil matrix¹¹.

There are four major mechanisms by which binding of any pesticide on soil surface^{21,22} occur viz. (i) physical adsorption, (ii) H-bonding, (iii) ion exchange, and (iv) coordination complexes.

(i) *Physical adsorption* : Van der Waal's attraction may be the principal forces causing adsorption of non-ionic, non-polar molecules or portion of the molecules. These forces also include short-range-forces charge induced dipole interactions, dipole induced dipole interactions and transient dipole induced dipole interaction. Van der Waal's forces are also involved in the adsorption of organic cations. Their contribution of these forces to adsorption is greatest for the ions in the vicinity of the surface as these forces decreases with distance.

(ii) *Hydrogen bonding* : Dipolar organic molecules adsorption onto clay surface is generally attributed hydrogen bonding of >C=O--- cation, >C=O---H₂O- cation, >N-H-O and C-H-O type. Hydrogen bonding has been suggested for adsorption of pesticides on soil and clay surfaces. The great importance of hydrogen-bonding is suggested as multiple sites being available to pesticide from both mineral and organic matter surface. The hydrogen bond of greatest importance is that associated with "Water Bridge" between the exchange cation and a polar organic molecule.

(iii) *Ion exchange* : Special significance to ion exchange is given with regard to the behavior and persistence of pesticides in soil, as pesticides adsorbed in this manner become particularly ineffective. Moreover, the adsorbed molecule may not be easily attacked by soil micro-organisms. Adsorption through ion-exchange is restricted to those pesticides which either exist as cation or which become positively charged through protonation.

Pesticides having low basicity may become cationic through protonation, either in soil solution or through adsorption. Whether protonation occurs or not depends on the basicity of the pesticide as shown by pK_a value and the proton-supplying capacity of the humic colloids. It is found that the adsorption decreases by the addition of a salt.

(iv) *Coordination* : Literature has shown that in determining the fate of pesticides in soil, coordination type of bonding may be quite important. Infrared spectroscopy has been employed by several workers to indicate the formation of coordination complexes between certain ligands and various metals on clays. The nature of the transition metal forming the coordinate complex on the clay determines whether or not the organic molecule will be degraded.

During the studies on adsorption of carbamate pesticides on soils and clays the author²³⁻²⁶ himself found that carbamate pesticides are adsorbed as :

Further the dissociation of water molecules in contact with exchangeable cations bring about proton formation, the degree of hydrolysis depends upon the polarizing power of the cations

The protons released bind the pesticide molecule to the clay surface by ionic bonding as :

Two adverse effects are caused by the strong binding of pesticide by soils. These are

(i) As lesser amount of pesticide is available for target and pest control is reduced

(ii) May cause injury to the plants. Injuries take place when residual pesticide becomes available from the soil particles to another crop. The amount is enough to cause injury to a sensitive rotational crop. This pesticide carry over may also lead to the presence of illegal residue on rotational food or feed crops.

Pesticide transfer Pesticide transfer is sometimes essential for pest control, e.g. for certain preemergence herbicide to be effective, they must move within the soil to reach the germinating seeds. Too much movement of pesticide led to reduce pest control, contamination of surface and ground water and injury to non-target species including humans. There are five paths for the transfer of pesticides: (a) volatilization, (b) runoff, (c) leaching, (d) absorption, (e) crop removal.

(a) Volatilization Volatilization is a process by which a pesticide is released to the atmosphere in the form of vapor or gas phase. The rate of volatilization of a pesticide is controlled mainly by the Henry's law constant²⁷. Pesticides having higher vapor pressure e.g. methyl bromide, dibromochloropropane, ethylene dibromide are more volatile. High environmental temperature and low relative humidity and more air movement increase the volatilization process while strong adsorption by soils decreases the volatilization. Soil conditions such as texture, organic matter content, soil moisture influences the pesticide volatilization^{28,29}.

More volatilization results not only air pollution, causing hazardous effects on field workers and nearby residents, but also results in reduced control³⁰ of the target pests as less pesticide remains at the target site. Some times, vapor can injure non target plants. Therefore, to

reduce pesticide volatilization, the highly volatile formulations must be avoided particularly in very hot and dry days.

(b) Runoff Runoff - takes place when water supply is faster than it enters the soil. Pesticides can be carried itself in the water or bound to eroding soil particles. Pesticide runoff is usually greater when heavy or sustained rains follow after an application. Over irrigation can lead to excess surface water, which also lead to pesticide runoff. Vegetation or crop residue tends to slow the movement of runoff water³¹. Runoff is also influenced by physical and chemical properties of pesticide³². Runoff pesticide causes injury to non-target plants, runoff into surface waters such as stream and ponds harm aquatic organisms. Pesticide runoff also leads to ground water contamination and can be injurious to crops³³, livestock or humans if contaminated water is used downstream.

The runoff of the pesticides can be decreased by monitoring of weather conditions, careful application of irrigation water, using a spray mix additive to enhance pesticide retention on foliage and incorporating the pesticide into the soil. Reduced tillage cropping system, strip cropping of untreated vegetation can also slow the movement of runoff water and help keep it out of wells, sinkholes, water bodies and other sensitive areas.

Leaching Leaching, the movement of pesticides through the soil depends on the pesticides chemical and physical properties. Strongly adsorbed pesticides leach less. Highly water soluble pesticides move easily^{34,35} in soil with water. Leaching of more persistent pesticides is high, leaching in sandy soil is much more than in clay. The method and rate of application, the use of tillage systems that modify soil conditions and the amount and timing of water a treated area receives after application can influence pesticide leaching³⁶.

A certain amount of leaching is essential for control of a target pests. Too much leaching, however can lead to reduced pest control, injury of non target species and ground water contamination. Besides monitoring weather conditions and the amount and timing of irrigation, careful selection of pesticides (which are more adsorbed, less persist and less water soluble) can minimize pesticide leaching.

Absorption or uptake : Absorption is the movement of pesticides into plants or microorganisms. Absorption of pesticides by target and non target organisms is influenced by environmental conditions and also by the physical and chemical properties of the pesticide and soil. There are four probable mechanisms of plant uptake³⁷ : (i) root uptake and transport to the higher plant parts, (ii) vegetative uptake of chemical vapors from air, (iii) external contamination by solid (i.e. soil or dust) followed by penetration into the soil and (iv) transport through oil cells in plants containing plant oil. Root uptake and vegetative uptake of vapors are the two main routes of plant contamination. Once absorbed by plants, pesticides may be broken down or they may remain in the plant tissue and may decay during harvest.

Crop removal : Crop removal transfers pesticides and their breakdown products from the treatment site. Most harvested food commodities are subject of washing and processing procedures that remove or degrade much of the remaining pesticides³⁸.

Pesticide degradation : Pesticide degradation or the breakdown of pesticide is usually considered beneficial. Pesticide destroying reactions change most pesticide residues in the environment to nontoxic or harmless compounds. However, degradation is detrimental when a pesticide is destroyed, before the target pest has been controlled. There are three types of pesticide degradation : (a) microbial, (b) chemical, (c) photo degradation.

(a) Microbial degradation is the breakdown of pesticides by fungi, bacteria and other microorganisms. The principal mechanisms of microbial activity are the catabolic and cometabolic degradation of substrates, their cross coupling to organic matter and their incorporation and accumulation³⁹. Catabolism is referred to as utilization of substrate as a source of energy and growth, and it will lead to the mineralization of either full or some portion and the remaining substance if any, accumulating in the soil. Cometabolism, on the other hand, refers to degradation without energy being derived from substrate oxidation to support growth⁴⁰. The later mechanism is the prevalence form of microbial metabolism pesticides in soil⁴¹. Soil conditions such as soil-moisture⁴², temperature⁴³, aeration⁴⁴, pH⁴⁵ and the amount of organic matter⁴⁶, structure and mobility of pesticides are the major factors which

affect the rate of microbial degradation as these factors affect microbial growth and activity. The nature of pesticides itself and its frequency of application is another factor which influences microbial degradation. Repeated applications of the same pesticide stimulate the buildup of organisms that are effective in degrading the chemicals. Microorganisms greatly reduce the effectiveness of these chemicals soon after application⁴⁷. The microbial degradation rates are known to vary from one soil to another soil and even within a specific soil.

In the microbial degradation process, the pesticide is absorbed into the cell membrane of the microbe. Enzymes present in the microbe breakdown the pesticide into smaller fragments with minerals as final end-product. The degradation process follows different pathways depending on microbes present.

The distribution of microbes in soil is not homogeneous. The population of microbes in the proximity of the surface is high which may be due to the fact that microbes naturally live on the material excreted from a plant's roots. Pesticides are generally degraded by microbes along with material excreted by the roots of plants.

Bacterial degradation dominates in soils and water at pH > 5.5, while in acidic medium soil fungal degradation dominates.

Microbial degradation is of two types, aerobic and anaerobic, and depends on surrounding conditions. Aerobic metabolism is a process where oxygen is utilized to oxidize the pesticide and occurs in soil, not in water as less oxygen is available. While in anaerobic degradation oxygen is not present, degradation occurs via some other pathway. In soils, the degradation of pesticides in the first layer is aerobic while below this layer it is anaerobic.

During microbial degradation reaction of pesticides, a large number of reactions have been observed viz. reduction, oxidation, hydrolysis, dealkylation, hydroxylation, ring cleavage and conjugation.

The most important degraders in soil are within the genera, *Arthobacter*, *Aspergillus*, *Alcaligenes*, *Bacillus*, *Corynebacterium*, *Flavobacterium*, *Fusarium*, *Nocardia*, *Penicillium*, *Pseudomonas* and *Trichoderma*. *Alcaligenes* and *Pseudomonas* are very good to degrade chloroaromatic pesticides⁴⁷. Fungus *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* is used

efficiently to degrade persistent pesticides like DDT or lindane. The organophosphorus pesticides are degraded by bacteria such as *Pseudomonas* sp., *Agrobacter*, *Arthrobacter* sp., *Flavobacterium* sp., fungi, *Fusarium*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Geobacillus caldxylosilyticus*, *Actinomyces*, *Streptomyces* etc., organophosphorus pesticides undergo microbial degradation via hydrolysis and/or via microbial cleavage. Enzymes phosphatase, esterase, hydrolyase and oxygenase participate actively in the degradation of organophosphorus pesticides. Carbamate pesticides are transformed metabolically by a variety of chemical reactions into more water soluble molecules with increased polar properties. The principal route of metabolism of carbamate esters is (i) via oxidation, oxidative reactions include (a) hydroxylation of aromatic ring, or epoxidation, (b) O-dealkylation, (c) N-methyl hydroxylation, (d) N-dealkylation, (e) hydroxylation and subsequent oxidation of aliphatic side chain and (f) thio ether oxidation to sulfoxides and sulfones; (ii) via hydrolysis, carbamates are hydrolysed by esterase to form amine, CO₂, alcohol or phenol. The microbial degradation of pyrethroid pesticides is very slow. Degradation of pyrethroids is brought about by a system of esterase and oxidase enzymes. Despite numerous years of study, little information is available concerning microbial population and community structure, proportion of community activity engaged in the transformation of pesticides and organic chemicals in soil. Relatively few microorganisms that degrade pesticides have been isolated and characterized.

The possibility of very rapid pesticide breakdown is reduced by using pesticides only when necessary and by avoiding repeated application of the same chemical. Alternating between different classes, groups or formulations of pesticides can minimize the potential for microbial degradation problems as well as pest resistance.

(b) Chemical degradation is the breakdown of pesticides by processes where living organisms are not involved. Hydrolysis, oxidation-reduction, substitution, elimination, dehalogenation and reduction, without the influence of microbial activities, are processes involved in chemical degradation. Hydrolysis is an important reaction that takes place in water and in soil for pesticide degradation. Chemical and physical properties of the pesticide, nature of substituents in the pesticide, soil type, temperature, soil pH, soil organic matter content, clay

content, soil moisture, and pesticide concentration, amount of sewage sludge in soil, effluent irrigation, and crop residue⁴⁸⁻⁵¹ are the major factors which determine the chemical reaction taking place.

Organochlorine compounds are resistant to chemical degradation in soil. DDT undergoes reductive dehalogenation at the trichloromethyl group and hydroxylation at the tertiary carbon to form alcohol⁵². Organophosphorus pesticides undergo oxidation by chlorine present in soil/water to convert P=S to P=O group. Organophosphorus esters like parathion, methidathion undergo hydrolysis to form alcohol and phosphoric acid^{53,54}. Carbamate pesticides oxamyl, methomyl widely used oxime pesticides undergo rapid degradation in anoxic and suboxic soil suspensions by a redox pathways involving Fe^{II}⁵⁵. During their studies on carbamate pesticides the author himself found that the degradation of carbamate pesticides increased with soil organic matter, soil surface area, % clay content, temperature, soil-moisture content⁵⁶, amending the soil with FYM. It was also found that degradation increased with pH, degradation was faster in alkaline medium⁵⁷. Pyrethroid pesticides undergo hydrolysis on the ester linkage and produce a number of metabolites. Hydroxylation of alcohol moiety at 2', 4', 5' or 6' position also occurs.

Chemical degradation can be prevented by not mixing the pesticide with certain fertilizers, other pesticides or water with specific characteristics. Degradation can also be reduced by mixing pesticides with buffers or other additives.

(c) Photo degradation is the process by which chemical bonds in pesticides are broken under the influence of light, including UV and visible range. In photolysis, light energy is absorbed by a pesticide molecule disrupting the pesticide's chemical structure (breaking chemical bonds) resulting in the formation of new chemical bonds and new chemical species. Photochemical reactions play a key role in environmental degradation of pesticides that contain organic chromophore or metal-organic complexes capable of absorbing light energy directly. Pesticides having no chromophore group undergo photosensitive reactions. Photodegradation of the pesticides in soils is increased in presence of soil organic matter like fulvic acid, humic acid, dyes like rose Bengal, pigments like chlorophyll, xanthone, secondary plant metabolites like ribofla-

vin, tyrosine etc. Surfactants used in various pesticide formulations act as photo sensitizer. During photochemical reaction, homolytic bond cleavage with the formation of free radical occurs. During photodegradation reaction of pesticides, free radicals $\cdot\text{CH}_3$, $\cdot\text{R}$, $\text{RO}\cdot$, $\text{ROO}\cdot$, $\text{NO}\cdot$, $\cdot\text{OH}$, $\cdot\text{NO}_3$ etc. are formed which require energy of approximately 400 kJ mol^{-1} (of $\sim 300 \text{ nm}$ wavelength). Photo-oxidation is one of the most prominent means of photodegradation initiated by various reactive species like singlet oxygen, free radicals, organic hydroxylperoxidase, hydrogen peroxidase etc. Photodegradation can destroy pesticides on foliage, on the surface or on the surface of soil, and even in the air.

Factors that influence pesticide photodegradation include the intensity of the sunlight, properties of the application site, the application method and the properties of pesticide. Photo chemically induced isomerisation, dimerisation and dechlorination are common reactions which are usually suffered by organo-chlorine pesticides⁵⁸⁻⁶⁰. Organophosphate pesticides undergo photo degradation mainly by ester cleavage, reduction, oxidation of thioether group, isomerisation, dealkylation, cyclisation, dimerisation etc.⁶¹. Carbamate pesticides undergo hydrolysis, oxidation, methylation and rearrangement reactions in presence of light^{62,63}.

Photodegradation can be reduced by adding the pesticides to the soil during or immediately after application.

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